

Furostan saponin and GC-MS study toward ascertaining the point of linkage between sugars moieties of spirostan saponin from the rhizomes of *Agapanthus africanus* (Linn.)

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Abstract : The linkage between the sugars moieties of antifungal spirostan saponin, (25*R*)-5 α -spirost-7-en-2 α ,3 β ,5 α -triol-3-*O*-{-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-*O*-[β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)]- β -D-glucopyranoside} of *Agapanthus africanus* (Linn.) have been determined by the analysis of GC-MS spectra of alditol acetates of the partially methylated sugars and the structures of the spirostan saponin and furostan saponin, 22-*O*-methyl-26-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(25*R*)-5 α -furostan-2 α ,3 β ,5 α ,9 α ,22 ζ ,26-hexitol-3-*O*-{-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-*O*-[β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)]- β -D-glucopyranoside} isolated from the rhizomes of the *A. africanus* have been established by various spectral evidences. This is the first report of furostan saponin in *A. africanus* rhizomes as well as first account of the use of GC-MS technique to ascertain the linkage between the saccharide moieties of the active constituent of the plant.

Keywords : *Agapanthus africanus* (Linn.), rhizomes, Liliaceae, furostan saponin, spirostan saponin, partially methylated alditol acetates, GC-MS analysis.

Introduction

Agapanthus africanus Linn. (Liliaceae) is a large erect evergreen herb of South African origin¹⁻³. A number of compounds, β -sitosterol, yuccagenin³, spirostan saponin^{4,5} and spirostan saponins^{6,7} have earlier been reported from this plant. Present study deals with the use of GC-MS technique⁸ to ascertain the assignment of the point of linkage between the sugar moieties of the antifungal spirostan saponin⁷, (25*R*)-5 α -spirost-7-en-2 α ,3 β ,5 α -triol-3-*O*-{-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-*O*-[β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)]- β -D-glucopyranoside}(1) and isolation of the known furostan saponin^{9,10}, 22-*O*-methyl-26-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(25*R*)-5 α -furostan-2 α ,3 β ,5 α ,9 α ,22 ζ ,26-hexitol-3-*O*-{-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-*O*-[β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)]- β -D-glucopyranoside}(2) from the rhizomes of the *A. africanus* (Linn.). This is the first report of the occurrence of furostan saponin in the rhizomes of *A. africanus* (Linn.) and the first account of the use of GC-MS technique⁸ to ascertain the point of linkage between the sugar moieties of the active constituent of the *A. africanus* (Linn.).

Results and discussion

Chromatographic resolution of crude *n*-butanol fraction of the ethanolic extract of the rhizomes of *A. africanus* (Linn.) afforded furostan saponin, 22-*O*-methyl-26-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(25*R*)-5 α -furostan-2 α ,3 β ,5 α ,9 α ,22 ζ ,26-hexitol-3-*O*-{-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-*O*-[β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)]- β -D-glucopyranoside} (2). The structure of furostan saponin 2 was confirmed by comparison of its physical and spectral data (IR, MS and ¹H NMR) with those reported in the literature^{9,10}. Earlier we isolated the active constituent⁷ 1 from the *n*-butanol fraction of the rhizomes of this plant was subjected to acid hydrolysis. The acid hydrolysis of compound 1 gave aglycone, (25*R*)-5 α -spirost-7-en-2 α ,3 β ,5 α -triol (1a) and sugar residue. The presence of sugars, D-glucose, D-galactose and L-rhamnose in 1 were identified by co-paper chromatography with authentic samples and aglycone 1a was identified by direct comparisons of its physical and spectral data with literature values⁶ and by direct comparisons with authentic sample. There was no report of

the use of GC-MS technique to determine the point of linkage between the sugar moieties of 1. Hence, in order to determine the sequence of sugar chain in the compound 1 from GC-MS study, it was permethylated. The permethylated product showed $[M+H+Na]^+$ ion peak at m/z 1080 in the FABMS positive spectrum. The increase in the molecular weight is corresponding to ten *O*-

ified as 1,3,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-2,4,6-tri-*O*-methyl hexitol and 1,5-di-*O*-acetyl-2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl hexitol by the GC-MS spectral data analysis. The result of the GC-MS analysis was also concordant to the two dimensional NMR (COSY) spectrum and finally, complete structure of 1 was ascertained by direct comparisons of the spectral data with those reported earlier^{7,9,10}.

methyl groups. The acid hydrolysis of permethylated 1 yielded partially methylated sugar, which were converted into their alditol acetates by treatment with sodium borohydride followed by acetylating with acetic anhydride and dry pyridine (Scheme 1). GC-MS spectra of the resulting alditol acetate of partially methylated sugars were analyzed and identified as 1,5-di-*O*-acetyl-6-deoxy-2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl hexitol, 1,2,3,5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-4,6-di-*O*-methyl hexitol and 1,5-di-*O*-acetyl-2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl hexitol⁸. Thus the point of linkage between the sugars of α -L-rhamnosyl unit was at C-2 (1 \rightarrow 2) and that of β -D-galactopyranosyl unit was at C-3 (1 \rightarrow 3) of the inner β -D-glucose moiety of 1 were ascertained. The point of linkage was further verified by Mannich hydrolysis of 1 to give disaccharide and L-rhamnose sugar. Disaccharide was further subjected to the same series of chemical reactions as 1 (Scheme 2) to give the alditol acetate of partially methylated respective sugars, which were identi-

Experimental

Plant material : The rhizomes of *Agapanthus africanus* (Linn.) were collected from Ootakamund (Tamilnadu), India and identified by Botany Division of Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, India. A specimen sample is kept in the Division.

Extraction and isolation : The rhizomes (15 kg) were dried, powdered and extracted with 95% ethanol. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure on rotatory evaporator at 50 °C and finally dried under vacuo to give solid mass (800 g). The ethanolic extract (500 g) was extracted successively with *n*-hexane and chloroform. The insoluble mass was then suspended with water and fractionated with *n*-butanol to give *n*-butanol and water fraction. All these fractions were evaporated in rotatory evaporator and dried under vacuo to furnish solid mass (300 mg from *n*-hexane, 700 mg from chloroform, 300 g from *n*-butanol and 198.6 g from water fraction). The *n*-butanol fraction (15 g) was chromatographed over silicon

Note

Mixture of partially methylated alditol acetates identified by GC-MS analysis

Scheme 1

gel (60–120 mesh, 500 g) column using chloroform and increasing amount of 5% aqueous methanol as the eluents. The eluents from chloroform : 5% aqueous methanol (13 : 7) and chloroform : 5% aqueous methanol (9 : 11) afforded fractions F021 and F024 respectively. Fraction F021 having compound 1 with coloring impurity was further purified by charcoaling to furnish 1 (8.98 g) as amorphous powder, R_f 0.56 (CHCl₃-5% aqueous CH₃OH, 3 : 2). Fraction F024 was flash chromatographed over silica gel (230–240 mesh) using gradient elution [eluting with chloroform : 5% aqueous methanol (3 : 2)] to give fraction F028. Fraction F028 was further subjected to HPLC with solvent system, methanol : water (3 : 2) to yield 2 (7.0 mg) as amorphous powder, R_f 0.34 (CHCl₃-5% aqueous CH₃OH, 3 : 2).

Acid hydrolysis of 1 :

A solution of 1 (30 mg) was refluxed with 2 N HCl in 80% aqueous ethanol (3 ml) for 4 h. It was then cooled, diluted with water and the ethanol evaporated. The aqueous, acidic hydrolysate was further heated at 100 °C for 1 h, cooled and extracted with *n*-butanol. The organic

layer was successively washed with NaHCO₃ and evaporated to give 1a (12 mg). The aqueous acidic phase was neutralized with Amberlite IR 410 (CO₃)²⁻ resin, filtered, concentrated and then subjected to co-paper chromatography using *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5) as a solvent and identified as D-glucose, D-galactose and L-rhamnose with authentic sample.

Permethylation of 1 :

Compound 1 (5 mg) was dissolved in dry DMSO (0.3 ml). To this was added finely powdered anhydrous NaOH (30 mg) and methyl iodide (0.3 ml) followed by stirring for 3 h at room temperature. Chloroform (1 ml) was added to the reaction mixture and centrifuged. Chloroform layer was separated and free alkali was washed with water and evaporated to dryness to furnish a viscous mass of permethylated 1 (4.5 mg).

Preparation of alditol acetates from permethylated 1 :

Permethylated 1 (3 mg) was refluxed with 2 N HCl in 80% aqueous ethanol (0.5 ml) for 4 h. The hydrolysate was then diluted with water, freed of ethanol by evaporation and further heated at 100 °C for 1 h. It was then

Mixture of partially methylated alditol acetates identified by GC-MS analysis

Scheme 2

neutralized with Amberlite IR 410 (CO₃²⁻) resin, concentrated to 0.5 ml and stirred with NaBH₄ (15 mg) at room temperature. After 2 h Amberlite IR 120 (H⁺) resin was added to maintain the pH 3.5 and the mixture was filtered, evaporated and co-distilled with three portions (5 ml, each) of methanol. The resulting mixture of alditol was treated with acid anhydride and dry pyridine (0.5 ml) for 2 h at 100 °C and the solvents were removed by co-distillation with toluene. The alditol acetate residues were subjected to GC-MS using a GLC column containing 3% of OV-1 at 160 °C. The results are summarized in the Table 1.

Mannich hydrolysis of 1 :

Compound 1 (10 mg) was stirred for 5 h with 2% concentrated HCl in dioxane (0.8 ml), then water (0.8

Table 1. GC-MS analysis of partially methylated alditol acetates obtained from 1

Alditol acetate	GC-MS (<i>m/z</i>)	Rt (min)
1,5-Di- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,3,4,6-tetra- <i>O</i> -methyl hexitol	205, 183, 173, 161, 145, 131, 129, 117, 113, 102, 101, 99, 87, 85, 81, 75, 71, 59	24.0
1,2,3,5-Tetra- <i>O</i> -acetyl-4,6-di- <i>O</i> -methyl hexitol	261, 201, 187, 161, 159, 130, 129, 127, 125, 117, 115, 111, 101, 100, 99, 87, 85, 71	26.16
1,5-Di- <i>O</i> -acetyl-6-deoxy-2,3,4-tri- <i>O</i> -methyl hexitol	175, 161, 145, 131, 117, 115, 101, 89, 87, 72, 69	21.93

ml) was added. Dioxane was removed at room temperature under reduced pressure. The hydrolysate was ex-

tracted with *n*-butanol and the organic layer was washed free of acid with water and evaporated to dryness. Chromatography of the residue over silica gel using chloroform containing increasing amount of 5% aqueous methanol (85 : 15) yielded a diglycoside of **1** (7 mg) and aqueous phase. The aqueous phase after neutralization with Amberlite 410 (CO₃²⁻) resin was found to contain L-rhamnose by co-paper chromatography with authentic sugar using solvent system *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5).

Permethylation and preparation of alditol acetates of the diglycoside of 1 obtained by Mannich hydrolysis :

Diglycoside was permethylated, the product was hydrolyzed and resulting partially permethylated sugars were converted in to their alditol acetates according to the procedure as given for **1**. The residue containing the partially methylated alditol acetates were subjected to GC-MS using GLC column containing 3% of OV-1 at 160 °C the result are given in the Table 2.

Table 2. GC-MS analysis of partially methylated alditol acetates obtained from diglycoside of **1**

Alditol acetate	GC-MS (<i>m/z</i>)	Rt (min)
1,3,5-Tri- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,4,6-tri- <i>O</i> -methyl hexitol	233, 203, 201, 189, 173, 161, 159, 157, 143, 129, 127, 117, 113, 101, 99, 87, 74, 71, 58	24.80
1,5-Di- <i>O</i> -acetyl-2,3,4,6-tetra- <i>O</i> -methyl hexitol	205, 173, 161, 145, 131, 129, 117, 113, 102, 101, 99, 87, 85, 81, 75, 71, 59	32.63

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